

REPRESENTING THE UNREPRESENTABLE: TRAUMA, SILENCE AND GUILT IN MUSLIM WAR NOVELS

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Abstract

This qualitative study examines the silence resulting from war trauma and the issues of representation of trauma, as portrayed in literary works, with particular focus on novels, *Curfewed Night* (2008) by Basharat Peer and *Born under a Million Shadows* (2009) by Andrea Busfield, highlighting the relationship between experience, memory and representation in structuring the understanding of trauma. The study addresses the gap between traumatic experience of war and the silencing of the survivors, which augment their suffering. Analyzing the characters in the selected novels, the research pins down as to how traumatic experiences cater silence, impeding the survivors to narrativize their stories. Considering the struggles of various characters along with those of the author-figure, Peer, in *Curfewed Night*, and examining the traumatic silence and ongoing suffering of Fawad and his mother in *Born under a Million Shadows*, the study seeks for possibilities of resilience in face of harrowing experiences of war and conflicts. Moreover, the study touches upon the wider implications of silence such as loss of connections and community life and challenges of articulation in both novels written in Kashmiri and Afghan contexts respectively. Furthermore, it also discusses the cyclic nature of trauma and suffering caused by recurring violence, further exacerbating the situation in these regions.

INTRODUCTION

The pervasive presence of violence, genocide, abuse, torture, terror, and war in the modern age has brought critical attention to the ways in which trauma is represented or, conversely, silenced (Wenzel et al, 2021). Wars have a history as long as mankind itself. Since antiquity man has waged wars for one thing or another such as honor, defense, supremacy, grandeur, survival, aggression and protection (Zargar, 1989). Since the latter half of the 20th Century Islamophobia and Muslim genocide, which have snowballed over time, the concept of wars have changed considerably than the traditional

concept of the term, catering many socio-politico-economic as well as psychological issues such as the traumatization, post-traumatic stress disorder PTSD, and trauma brain injury TBI. The psychological traumatization and the need to intellectualize it have become crucial in the modern times. The lasting impact of these traumatic encounters, render the victims petrified and apprehensive, losing grip on social values and personal integrity. Hence, in modern times, psychological trauma has become increasingly pervasive concern, leading to a growing mental health problem (Lopez, 2024).

The present study digs deep into the complex psychological issues encapsulating the conceptualization and cognition of trauma, specifically in the backdrop of Kashmir and Afghan wars, and the way these issues cater considerable challenges in their representation, rendering the victims silent. Wood (1988) observes, "The history of pain becomes the writing of silence," alluding to the tensions and unresolved issues suffered by the authors and characters navigating the challenges of representation of trauma and the subsequent silence. By investigating both novels, the study intends to highlight the crucial issues of silenced stories and the effect of trauma on individuals as well as communities undergoing war in these contexts.

1.1. Research Statements

This study examines the multifarious nature of trauma, resulting from war and violent conflicts in the Muslim world, with particular focus on Kashmir and Afghanistan. The study reveals the characters' struggle with silencing and narrativization of their trauma; memory and issues of articulation, illuminating how trauma impedes storytelling and leads to individual and collective silence on the part of the survivors.

1.2. Objectives

1. Detect particular instances of silence demonstrated by various characters in the selected novels in context of their experiences of war-trauma in the backdrop of Kashmir and Afghan wars.
2. Ascertain the challenges and barriers confronted by the characters attempting to narrativize and represent their trauma.
3. Examine the consequences of silence induced by psycho-social factors and see how it leads to individual and collective periodic trauma.

1.3. Questions

1. How do various characters in the selected novels demonstrate silence and psycho-social issues impeding the representation of their trauma?
2. What can be the consequences of long-term silence on the part of trauma survivors as depicted in the novels from Kashmiri and Afghan background?

2. Research Methodology

This is a qualitative study which employs comparative approach to text-based analysis of the selected novels, involving close reading technique with particular focus on character's dialogues and introspection, descriptive passages and authorial commentary, thereby illustrating trauma and silence in both novels. It also focuses on the narrative strategies used to portray trauma and silence such as speech interruptions, thoughts unspoken and authors' reflections on the representational issues. The study undertakes a detailed character analysis in both novels, investigating trauma's detrimental effect on behavior, relationships and social interactions of the victims. The study then compares and contrasts the portrayal of trauma and silence in two different conflict zones and narratives.

This qualitative study explores the intricate relationship between war trauma, the resulting silence, and its representation in Basharat Peer's *Curfewed Night* and Andrea Busfield's *Born under a Million Shadows*. This conceptual standpoint focuses on the idea that profound experiences of war claim a heavy toll on the psychological health of the victims, inflicting irreparable injuries which often lead to silence as the easiest way of coping with trauma or "freeze" as "a state of detached calm" (Habeeb, 2015). However, this freezing turns to be periodic and exacerbates the miserable condition of the victim, eroding connections with society.

The study further posits that literary representation becomes a crucial site for understanding and potentially breaking this silence. By analyzing the narratives of characters and authorial voices, the research investigates the struggles and strategies employed in articulating traumatic memories. The framework acknowledges the potential for literature to bridge the gap between lived experience, memory, and its communication, offering insights into the psychological and social consequences of silence in Kashmiri and Afghan contexts.

The study centers on the following assumptions:

1. War trauma inherently carries the potential to induce silence in survivors as a psychological response to overwhelming experiences.

2. Memory of traumatic events is central to understanding the experience of war trauma and its subsequent representation or lack thereof.

3. Literary narratives offer a valuable lens through which to examine the complexities of war trauma, silence, and the struggle for representation.

4. Silence resulting from war trauma has significant negative consequences for the individual's psychological well-being and the social fabric of affected communities.

5. The act of representing trauma, even amidst challenges, holds the potential for fostering understanding, empathy, and potentially contributing to individual and communal resilience.

3. Discussion

3.1. Bearing witness to Silence: Trauma and the Unspoken in Curfewed Night

In an era defined as the era of violence and war, the silence or crisis of representation of trauma becomes a topic of hot debate. The cognition and dissemination of trauma's meanings and potential suffering becomes increasingly challenging for the victims, inducing silence. Silence stands for the incapacity or aversion from voicing out the agonizing traumatic events which is the direct consequence of actual or threatened power causing psychological harm (World Health Organization, 2003). Peer's memoir depicts the complex relationship among experience, remembrance and narrativization, claiming how trauma and silence augment the sufferings of the survivors impeding the narrative reconstruction of and eventual processing of their trauma. The work portrays a prolonged legacy of war in face of silenced victims. The author of the book painstakingly incorporates the marginalized and silenced voices in contradiction to official histories, thus challenging the ongoing silence. This section studies the silence forced on various characters including the author, whose own silence screams aloud and sets the stage for the silences to come ahead. Notwithstanding the apparently empowering transformation, Shahid, a friend of Peer and a doctor in the community, comments, "people like you and me are a privileged minority in Kashmir" (146), alluding to Peer's temporary evasion and continued silence in the face of brutal reality of Kashmir. Ever since his childhood, the start of the

conflict, the inner turmoil caused by the harrowing experiences and memories of the military and militant operations in Kashmir, he could not initially recognize "how brutal brutality could be" (121). In the later years, his confrontation with other peoples' trauma precipitates his own silence. He confesses: I shared some stories with a few friends in Delhi, but I could never say everything. I would find myself in the middle of a sentence, choked, rendered inarticulate by memory. The telling even in the shade of intimacy, was painful. (Peer, 2008, p. 98)

Struggling to find "escape in journalism" (161), coveting to pen down the memories long held in his bosom, Peer detests himself being infidel to these recollections (153), trying to overpower his "own ghosts" (154). He justifies this by saying that the one who encounters trauma survivors like himself, has to face petulance and "pointless arguments" (153). His deep emotional connection to the land has made him vulnerable, given the funerals triggering "depressions for days to come" (169). Dreading he would become a "voyeur", Peer averts meeting Ansar who has been imprisoned at Papa 2 (16) a notorious detention cell set up by the Indian army to torture Kashmiri captives. He admits:

I spent my afternoons reading and tried to write in the evenings. But I could not distance from the experiences I was trying to process and shape in words. I sulked, turned irritable, and had pointless arguments with friends...this is common among people who come into contact with trauma victims. (Peer, 2008, p. 153)

The narrative depicts many an instance of silence. Such as Peer's powerlessness to speak about the gang rape of women at Kunan and Poshpura villages in 1990. Silence is the fatal consequence of violence, deepening the effects of trauma by denying security, processing and differentiating between past and present. However, "trauma will out" itself even when denied and silenced Merwe & Gobodo-Madikizela (2008). Shafi, another prisoner at Papa-2, suddenly stops midway when recollecting the torture he suffered. "I can't talk about it. It makes me crazy" (146), he confesses helplessly.

Such agonizing experiences can be processed off by breaking the silence. Briston, (cited in Dyson et al, 2015), extols the power of self, being "autonomous" yet "socially dependent", susceptible to pain yet

adept to retrieval in the presence of “empathic others” (p. 3). Similar silence is observed by Hussain, another victim of conflict, hit by profound trauma and forced to resolute silence, fearing the healing impossible. In such situation, the victim needs a sense of safety and security to “fully share his story” (Heberle, 2001). LaCapra advocates that severe psychological injury can incur a feeling that escape is impossible. The silence observed by Hussain reflects this mental state, apprehending his words would become a source of deficiency for him. To break his silence he must overcome his shame and fears and being able to segregate between the past and the present.

The articulation of trauma has limits as language can only depict what is absent or what is present. Loss of community life and social connections, which directly result from trauma, cause isolation and alienation to the survivor also dubbed as “singularity, estrangement, and solitude” (Stolorow, 2007). An example can be Mubina’s trauma who is estranged from the rest of the community she is part of (159). Hence, the silence becomes integral part of the memoir with the author trying to honor the “unspeakabilities” (Norris, cited in Mackinnon, 2009).

3.2. Trauma and the Silence of Innocence in Afghanistan

Like Paer, Busfield illustrates the trauma suffered by the innocent civilians victims of Afghan war, typified by the protagonist, Fawad and Mariya, his mother. The happy family of five ends, when his father joins the Northern Alliance against the Taliban’s oppressive regime across the country, followed by the demise of their eldest son a year later, dramatically worsening their socio-economic standing in the community. Their days and nights then undergo by the nocturnal raids of Taliban. At one such night, during these raids Fawad’s life changes forever after the profound traumatic event which he suffers. He recalls:

I heard the fear in my mother’s voice when one night she shook me awake to pull me into her arms and carry me from my bed to the corner of the kitchen where my sister and brother were waiting. I remember it clearly now: my mother was trembling through her clothes and outside I could hear the

sound of heavy trucks filling the street with the noise of their heavy engines” (Busfield, 2009, p. 157)

As he hid in the Kitchen, Fawad could clearly hear his mother “crying, and, outside, shouts and screams invaded the stillness of the night” (157) as “five black shadows” materialized over their heads. This vivid memory of pain accentuates the excruciating reminiscences of trauma. Herman comments that such traumatic recollections reconstruct the memory and trauma becomes a part of the “life story” of the victim (1992, p. 175). The mother, trying to protect her children, undergoes a sexual assault by the Taliban, “ripping at her clothes.” Desperate, she yelled at Fawad, “run, Fawad run,” trying him away from seeing the molestation happen to her. Before fleeing to the nearby bushes, Fawad, however, is relieved to see another Talib pulling the attacker away from his mother and angrily pushing him outside. Hiding in the bushes, Fawad witnessed “the whole world catch fire” as his house along with the whole village was set by the Taliban ablaze.

Devastated, they shifted to Paghman, at their aunt’s where, in spite of the silence wrapped around this horrific incident, everyone suffered. Fawad could not overlook “the look in my mother’s eyes. It was one of death, and the blackness that went with it was mirrored in the eyes of Bilal” (160). They lost their sister which turned his mother silent, while Bilal, his brother, hampered by the guilt of failure to protect his family “was now lost to the Afghan obsession with revenge” (160), crying “giant tears of anger,” feeling he “should have done more to protect” them, but being “only a boy” against “an army of black turbaned devils,” he did what was possible. Hitherto, disburbed by “shame and dishonor,” he finally followed the footsteps of his father to join the Northern Alliance, conforming the Afghan tradition of “war and revenge,” never to be seen afterwards (161). As the Northern Alliance entered Kabul, they silently assumed his death.

A similar trauma is suffered by Spandi, Fawad’s friend. Having lost his mother and sister, fathered by an addict who has nothing to offer his family except hunger and violence, his suffering is not very different from Fawad. Fawad rightly comments, “We just carry with us differing versions of the same story” (148). Another such example of profound trauma and resolute silence is found in Pir Hedri who is also

haunted by his memories of war. One day, lost in the recollections of devastation brought by Russian invasion, he describes:

We lost a lot of good men that day...all committed to the cause of freedom...they had just carried out a dared daylight attack on a Russian base north of Kunar. Hundreds of enemy soldiers died in the assault, caught unaware by the sheer daring of our raid and knocked senseless...and as quickly as they appeared, rising from nowhere to unleash hell on the Russians, they melted away again, like ghosts drifting back into the landscape. (Busfield, 2009, p. 51).

Pir Hedri's description of Taliban's occupation, "the Taliban were bastards...most of them were small men from small villages who had never been taught to read and write. Hell, even their leaders were illiterate" (70), speaks about his disillusionment of war. At Fawad's rhetorical question (How could they manage to rule if they had been so illiterate?), Pir Hedri answers ironically, "through fear" and Fawad aids this fear factor by recounting the story of "a woman who had all her fingers cut off by the religious police just because she'd colored her nails" (72).

Haji Khalid Khan, an influential Afghan Warlord, has also had his own painful memory of trauma in face of molestation and eventual murder of his wife and daughter as revenge to his fight against the Taliban, making him silent "almost numb with grief" (177) and turning him to self-destruction and vengeful violence, reflecting the "shocks, numbing, confusion, disorientation, anxiety, intense fears and a sense of abandonment" which are usual in face of war's psychic impact. Fawad truly comments, "There is no one of us that is not touched by them in one way or another," with loss and poverty being widespread (99).

Another character in the novel, Pir the Madman, also suffers his own traumatic memories of the past, a silent survivor of Afghan adversities (237). The very sight of the Madman turns Fawad sad, wondering, "at some time in his life he must have been a boy like me with everything to look forward to" (237), illuminating the unrepresentable suffering that war can inflict. The war goes on and so does the trauma. The ever increasing insurgence and frequent blasts indicate the worsening situation.

The discussion above portrays a poignant picture of the trauma induced silence in various characters. For example, Fawad's mother grows silent after losing her family slowly and devastatingly, first her husband then her son and daughter. Bilal resorts to silence owing to the shame and guilt of failing to protect his family and eventually succumbing to revenge. Haji Khan's profound trauma leads him to silence to the extent of numbness caused by acute grief. Pir, the Madman's personality is all shrouded in silence, his untold and unwarranted story resonates with the character and pervades the air. In short, the silence becomes a forceful weapon, indicating the profound emotional and psychological toll of war, with individuals incapacitated and unwilling to speak out their pain, burdened by the enormity of suffering. This is a sort of self-preservation, a coping mechanism against the experiences too devastating to be shared or processed. The want of discussion among the characters further accentuates the inescapable silence where the shared memories can create an unspeakable cognition of their suffering.

Conclusion

War trauma in *Curfewed Night* and *Born Under a Million Shadows* profoundly induces silence as a psychological defense, making the articulation of horrific experiences nearly impossible, exemplified by various character's breakdown and the pervasive unspoken grief within the novels. The struggle to represent this trauma is a central theme, evidenced by Peer's inability to write about *Papa-2* and the often stark, emotionally charged yet incomplete, nature of Fawad's narration, highlighting the inherent limitations of language when confronting unspeakable events. This silence has significant negative consequences, isolating individuals, hindering the necessary processing of grief, and fracturing communal bonds, as illustrated by Mubeena's social estrangement. Despite the immense challenges, the act of attempting to give voice to traumatic experiences, as both Peer and Fawad undertake, even imperfectly, offers a crucial pathway towards fostering understanding, empathy, and ultimately, individual and communal resilience in the long shadow of war.

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